

How the oxygen absorption affects the Al₂O₃ encapsulated blue phosphorene-Au alloy

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The urgent quest to introduce the Xenes, a new family of graphene-like materials, into everyday technological devices further demands for a specific understanding of their reactivity to different environments. Here, the role of oxygen on the blue phosphorene fragments alloyed with Au(111) substrate, so called BlueP-Au alloy, is investigated either on a microscopic scale or at the interface with Al₂O₃, commonly used to protect Xenes in ambient conditions. Although molecular oxygen does not affect the BlueP-Au alloy nor intercalate below it, the role of oxygen is fundamental to relief the charging effects at the very interface between Al₂O₃ and BlueP-Au alloy when exposed to air. These findings highlight the importance of combining different tools, including microscopy and spectroscopy, to ascertain the stability of two-dimensional materials in device-ready configurations.

1. Introduction

The Xenes are today an emerging two-dimensional (2D) materials family including artificial graphene-like materials discovered soon after the isolation of their carbon-based progenitor.^[1] Among them, the honeycomb lattices made of elements of the column IVA (below carbon) attracted much interest because of their potential applications in the electronics industry, like silicon and germanium, or for recent outcomes related to topological physics, like tin.^[2-4] Xenes like silicene, germanene, and stanene show properties akin to graphene and the increasing mass

of the X element from carbon to tin enables the opening of a bandgap due to spin-orbit coupling effects, *e.g.* up to 0.3 eV for stanene on Cu(111),^[5] compatible with technological applications, especially in the electronics field, where graphene suffers from intrinsic limitation.^[1] Another route to reach out the same goal, *i.e.* bandgap opening, is looking at neighbors elements of IVA column. In this framework, the exfoliation of black phosphorous, the most stable allotrope of phosphorous, resulted into a new 2D material called phosphorene.^[6] Similar to graphene, also phosphorene obtained from mechanical exfoliation possesses a counterpart called blue phosphorene (or blue phosphorous in its layered form) that does not exist in nature, as predicted by theoretical calculations.^[7] The structure of blue phosphorene is closer to silicene than black phosphorene and its bandgap decreases from 2 eV in the single layer to ~ 1.2 eV for bulk.^[7] The first attempts to artificially create blue phosphorene were based on molecular beam epitaxy (MBE) of evaporated black phosphorous on metallic substrate, *i.e.* Au(111), following avenues traced by silicene on Ag(111).^[8] Although the experimental results achieved by Zhang *et al.* were successfully replicated by other groups,^[9-13] some inconsistencies in the blue phosphorene structure arrangement on the Au(111) eventually led to the conclusion that blue phosphorene fragments are alloyed with the gold atoms of the templates.^[14,15] Nonetheless an encapsulation and transfer process for the blue phosphorene fragments alloyed with gold atoms (hereafter BlueP-Au alloy) has been already developed and is based on the BlueP-Au alloy sandwiched in between Al₂O₃ capping layer (as for other Xenon)^[16] and thin gold films on mica.^[9] Intriguingly, freestanding-like blue phosphorene can be successfully synthesized by means of silicon intercalation of the BlueP-Au alloy.^[17] A similar intercalation mechanism (by means of oxygen) has been already reported for silicene on Ag(111) thus resulting in a quasi-freestanding silicene.^[18] Nonetheless, the BlueP-Au alloy system is also interesting as an intriguing example of the metal-phosphorous networks (inspired by the so-called metal-organic networks) that, in this specific case, can be artificially grown by MBE.^[14] In light of these considerations and the proven air instability of the BlueP-Au alloy when exposed to ambient conditions,^[9] here the

role of molecular oxygen on the atomic structure of BlueP-Au alloy as well as the role of air on the electrostatics at the Al₂O₃/BlueP-Au alloy interface are investigated in order to find viable routes for the blue phosphorene synthesis and encapsulation aiming at real-world applications.

2. Role of oxygen molecules on BlueP-Au alloy

In the framework of the chemical stability of Xenos, the oxidation of silicene grown on Ag(111) was initially studied through X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and only recently Du *et al.* investigated the molecular oxygen role on the intercalation on bilayer silicene islands on the same substrate.^[18,19] Recently we have demonstrated via XPS that in the case of BlueP-Au alloy grown by MBE on Au(111) thin films on mica (see Experimental Section/Methods), the chemical reactivity upon oxygen exposure is very low.^[9] However, a microscopic characterization to elucidate the possible intercalation of molecular oxygen with oxygen doses comparable with those used by Du *et al.* (up to 1200 L) has not been reported yet. Reversible oxidation on the BlueP-Au alloy was already investigated with higher doses (>18000 L) to study the fundamental pathways of the degradation mechanism.^[20] **Figure 1a** shows the characteristic flower-like pattern of the BlueP-Au alloy observed by scanning tunneling microscopy (STM).^[9] This pattern is originated by blue-phosphorene subunits coaxed together with gold atoms thus forming a 2D ordered network on the Au(111) surface.^[14] **Figure 1b** shows the same surface after 2000 L of molecular oxygen exposure where clusters with different height and dimension can be observed (compare the line profiles in Figure 1a with those in Figure 1b taken before and after the exposure to O₂). As highlighted by the line profiles in Figure 1a and b the typical height of the clusters above each blue-phosphorene subunit lies between 1 and 2 Å. Although the atomic structure of the larger clusters can be hardly accessed by STM investigation, the topographic image in Figure 1b shows also the presence of small bright spots (denoted by red arrows) located at various position on the triangular-shaped petals

of the flowerlike BlueP-Au alloy pattern, that can be identified as oxygen atoms adsorbed on the surface, as already reported in literature.^[20]

Figure 1. (a) STM images of $(20 \times 20) \text{ nm}^2$ of the BlueP-Au alloy before and (b) after the exposure to 2000 L of O_2 . STM profiles are reported along the green and blue lines traced in the topographic images.

3. Role of oxygen on Al_2O_3 encapsulated BlueP-Au alloy

Even if the STM analysis proves that the BlueP-Au alloy is unaffected by *in situ* doses of molecular oxygen, when exposed to dry air the BlueP-Au alloy undergoes oxidation.^[9] A viable option enabling to take the BlueP-Au alloy out of an ultra-high vacuum (UHV) environment is growing a capping layer on top. We already demonstrated that a thin layer made of Al_2O_3 can hinder the oxidation of the underlying Xenon and of the BlueP-Au alloy as well.^[9,16] The Al_2O_3 capping does not alter the chemical stability of the BlueP-Au alloy outside the growth environment as well as in a wet environment like the tetrahydrofuran bath, being able to significantly slow down the oxidation process after a prolonged air exposure.

Figure 2. (a) XPS of the Au 4f core level measured before and after the Al₂O₃ deposition on an Au(111) reference sample. (b) 5 nm-thick Al₂O₃ encapsulated BlueP-Au alloy measured after 3 and 20 days of ambient conditions exposure. (c) as (b) with a thinner (2.5 nm) Al₂O₃ capping layer.

Although stoichiometric, the MBE-grown Al₂O₃ protection layer is characterized by the presence of fixed intrinsic charges which alter the electrostatic charge neutrality condition at the Al₂O₃/BlueP-Au alloy interface by creating an interfacial space charge region.^[16,19,21]

Figure 2a shows the XPS spectra of the Au 4f core levels measured from a reference Al₂O₃/Au(111) sample and it can be noticed that after Al₂O₃ deposition the Au 4f core levels are shifted at higher binding energy (of 0.4 eV). An even larger shift (0.7 eV) is also observed after Al₂O₃ deposition on BlueP-Au alloy (**Figure 2b**), that turns out to increase the charging effect originally observed in the reference sample. Interestingly, we observe that the Au 4f core levels backshift toward the pristine binding energy (84.0 eV) position when the Al₂O₃ capped BlueP-Au alloy samples are exposed to air as illustrated by the dashed arrows in Figure 2b, thus suggesting that oxygen chemisorption in defect sites of the Al₂O₃ capping layer may induce a partial neutralization of the interfacial space charge region. By comparison, the large shift can be explained by the blue phosphorene fragments that, even if alloyed with the gold substrate, constitute an additional barrier for the photoemitted electrons of the Au(111) surface, thus

resulting in a continuous 2D layer as evidenced by the STM images of Figure 1. On the other hand, the P $2p$ core level is unaffected by oxygen incorporation in the Al_2O_3 capping layer even after months.^[9] We notice that charging effect is dependent on the capping layer thickness as we observe a comparatively lower binding energy shift (0.5 eV) when the capping layer thickness is reduced down to 2.5 nm. This behavior can be inherently related to the amount of incorporated fixed charge in the capping layer.

This picture is corroborated by conductive atomic force microscopy (C-AFM) analysis carried out *ex situ* in contact mode. C-AFM has been applied to map the current leakage under a constant applied bias (2.5 V) through the thin 5 nm thick Al_2O_3 capping layer both in the Al_2O_3 /BlueP-Au alloy and in the reference Al_2O_3 /Au(111), see sketch in **Figure 3**. The results of this analysis for the Al_2O_3 /BlueP-Au alloy sample are reported in Figure 3b and c. From the current maps we notice that the Al_2O_3 surface, although uniform in the topographic image (Figure 3b), is characterized by the appearance of isolated spots of high electrical conductivity (bright yellow regions in Figure 3c). These regions are present in both samples thus suggesting not only that the Al_2O_3 , albeit stoichiometric, has a defective nature but also that the BlueP-Au alloy does not hinder the formation of electrically conductive paths through the gold substrate and the AFM tip. In this framework, the artificial engineering of a 2D metal-phosphorous network could be another route to achieving atomic-thin memristors as recently proposed for the MoS_2 -Au case.^[22] We note that the observed defects of the Al_2O_3 matrix (oxide defects) may be at the origin of fixed charges at the Al_2O_3 /BlueP-Au alloy interface.^[21]

A deeper insight into this aspect is provided by the electrostatic force microscopy (EFM) investigation of both the samples. In the EFM, the electrostatic force acting on the AFM tip induces a shift of the resonance phase condition (φ) in response to a bias voltage (V_g) applied at the Au substrate according to:

$$|\tan \varphi| \sim \frac{Q_f C(z)}{k} \frac{V_g^2}{z^2} \quad (\text{eq.1})$$

where Q_f and k are the quality factor and spring constant of the AFM cantilever, respectively, $C(z)$ the electrical capacitance between the substrate and the conductive AFM tip separated by the distance z , Figure 3a. [23–25]

Figure 3. (a) Schematic view of C-AFM and EFM experiments performed on the Al_2O_3 encapsulated BlueP-Au alloy. (b) AFM topography and (c) C-AFM image (bias 2.5 V) of $(1 \times 1) \mu m^2$ area taken on Al_2O_3 /Blue-P alloy sample. (d) plot and fit of the $|tg(\Phi)|$ values at different gate voltages for the Al_2O_3 /BlueP-Au alloy (black squares) and Al_2O_3 /Au (red squares) derived from the EFM measurements

According to Equation 1, the change in the slope of the function $|tg(\Phi)|$ vs. V_g^2 , reported in Figure 3d, indicates that the electrical capacitance varies more than 10% within the two samples, in particular $C(z)$ decreases in the capped BlueP-Au alloy (1.10×10^{-19} F) compared to the reference sample (1.24×10^{-19} F). In a simplified picture, these findings hint to a change of the

electrical charges induced at the AFM tip ($C \sim V/Q$) because of the electrostatic screening potential of the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{BlueP-Au}$ alloy stack. We can speculate that this effect is the result of the competition between the large electronic polarizability expected in atomically thin materials and the presence of free charges connected with oxide defects in the Al_2O_3 capping layer.^[21,23,26] In order to confirm the surmise that defects in the Al_2O_3 become preferential adsorption sites for oxygen when the samples are exposed to air, we reintroduced them back in UHV to check their chemical status. **Figure 4** reports the XPS core levels of O $1s$ and Al $2s$. The usually scrutinized Al $2p$ core level is not reported for discussion here because very close to the P $2p$ and hence affected by its background.^[9] For a stoichiometric Al_2O_3 capping layer the O $1s$ core level is placed at 532.5eV whereas Al $2s$ is at 120.5 eV, *i.e.* +2.5 eV from the metallic Al state.^[19] After air exposure and hence oxygen chemisorption, we observe a rigid shift in both O $1s$ and Al $2s$, nearly comparable with that observed in the Au $4f$ core levels (see Figure 2b). The O $1s$ core level shape progressively becomes asymmetric with a tail at higher binding energy (Figure 4a), that can be associated with hydroxyl groups (-OH) adsorption.^[27] Conversely, the Al $2s$ core level shows a tail at lower binding energy (see Figure 4b) that is related to a residual metallic component caused by the Al_2O_3 deposition process, which consists of a pre-deposition of a first Al layer to prevent oxidation of the underlying Xene.^[16,19] After 3 days exposure, both O $1s$ and Al $2s$ core levels are shifted to lower binding energy (of 0.5 and 0.6 eV, respectively, see Figure 4) and their binding energy do not change after the 20 days long exposure. It takes up to 20 days instead to progressively restore the pristine binding energy of the Au $4f$ core levels. On one hand, this behavior explains why this so-grown capping layer is effective to protect the underlying 2D layer, *i.e.* the charge compensation occurs on a scale of days, but, on the other hand, for specific applications, *e.g.* electronic devices, developing additional protective layers is highly demanded. Recently, a viable option was proposed by adding an atomic layer deposition made Al_2O_3 capping layer on top of the amorphous one.^[28]

Figure 4. (a) XPS of the O 1s and (b) Al 2s core levels of BlueP-Au alloy sample measured after the Al₂O₃ growth, 3 and 20 days of exposure to ambient air.

4. Conclusion

In summary, we have elucidated the reactivity of molecular oxygen both on the pristine and on the Al₂O₃ encapsulated BlueP-Au alloy surfaces. Our findings indicate the interaction of molecular oxygen with both the interfaces occurs on different circumstances. Oxygen is adsorbed on top of the pristine BlueP-Au interface but does not compromise the structural integrity nor intercalate through the crystalline structure of the alloy. Conversely, the oxygen incorporation into the Al₂O₃ matrix encapsulated BlueP-Au is promoted at oxide defects sites and manifested by a change in the binding energy of the aluminum and oxygen atomic species as measured by XPS. Such effect satisfactorily accounts for the partial neutralization of the intrinsic fixed charges observed as soon as the as-grown ultrathin Al₂O₃ oxide is exposed to air. However, a different behavior is observed by comparison between reference Al₂O₃/Au and Al₂O₃/BlueP-Au/Au samples. These outcomes show that for real-world applications based on Xenes, a deeper understanding of their chemical reactivity towards ambient environment as well as the electrostatics at the interface with oxide should be taken into account. Moreover, the formation of a metal-phosphorous network, arranged in a crystalline 2D layer, might pave the

way to a new class of Xene derivatives with different properties, where Xene fragments alloyed with the hosting metal substrates could be atomically tailored and engineered.

5. Experimental Section/Methods

MBE growth and O₂ exposure: Experiments were carried out in a UHV (base pressure 10⁻¹⁰ mbar) system equipped with three interconnected chambers for sample growth via MBE, chemical analysis via XPS, and morphological characterization via STM. Clean ~300 nm Au(111)/mica substrates were prepared by repeated Ar⁺ bombardment (1 kV, 1×10⁻⁶ mbar) and subsequent annealing at 500 °C for 30 min. Phosphorus was deposited by evaporation from a crucible containing bulk black phosphorus. During the deposition process, the substrate temperature was kept in between 240 and 270 °C. The temperature readings were crosschecked by pyrometer-based calibration of the thermocouple attached under the sample holder. An Al₂O₃ capping layer is grown *in situ* by co-deposition of an aluminum beam from a k-cell and ultra-pure molecular oxygen. The Al₂O₃ thickness is measured *ex situ* via AFM. Ultra-pure O₂ was introduced in the growth chamber by a leak valve at a partial pressure of 1.3 × 10⁻⁶ mbar. The oxygen dose was 2000 L (where 1 L = 1 s at 1.3 × 10⁻⁶ mbar).

STM and XPS measurements: STM images were acquired at room temperature with a homemade tungsten tip pre-calibrated onto a HOPG surface. STM topographies were typically acquired at -1.3 V and 0.3 nA setpoint. XPS measurements have been carried out *in situ* with nonmonochromatized Mg (1253.6 eV) at a take-off angle of 37°.

C-AFM and EFM: *Ex situ* C-AFM and EFM investigations were carried out with a commercial AFM-Bruker Dimension Edge. For the C-AFM, the microscope was equipped with a tunnelling-AFM electrometer (TUNA) with 1 pA - 1 μA current range. Current maps were acquired in contact mode using highly doped diamond-coated tips (CDT-CONTR, nanosensor™) with typical radius of curvature of ~100 nm. A bias voltage (2.5 V) was applied to the substrate, while the tip was electrically grounded. The EFM investigations were carried

out in tapping mode with conductive Pt/Ir coated tips in a dual pass scan. In the first scan the topography was acquired with the tip electrically grounded, in the second scan the phase signal was acquired withdrawing the tip at a lift height of 30 nm above the surface and applying a DC electrical signal varied in the range 1-7 V. Note that the dual pass scan hinders artifacts due to topography crosstalk.

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